

Key Risks from permafrost thaw – a comparative, trans- and interdisciplinary risk assessment

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Permafrost degradation has far-reaching consequences for the global climate and profound impacts on local and regional livelihoods (Doloisio and Vanderlinden 2020; Povoroznyuk and Schweitzer 2023; Ramage et al. 2022). We here present an inter- and transdisciplinary analysis of key risks associated with permafrost thaw across several sites along and near Arctic coasts. While the permafrost-climate feedback is well-documented (Schoor et al. 2015), the impacts on coupled socio-ecological systems of the permafrost region remain understudied. In addition to ongoing fast changes in the environment, the Arctic coastal region is characterised by strong geopolitical tensions and undergoes rapid societal transformations, making it essential to understand the implications of permafrost thaw on Arctic coastal communities. With this study, we aim to contribute to the growing body of research on climate-related hazard and risk assessments in the Arctic, as well as on vulnerability, resilience, and adaptation.

METHODS AND METHODOLOGY

The “Nunataryuk” project, led by the Alfred Wegener Institute, has carried out a comprehensive six-year investigation into rapidly changing permafrost regions in the North. Between 2019 and 2023 Nunataryuk scientists in collaboration with local experts used a mixed-methods approach to collect extensive information on physical processes, uncertainties, and societal concerns in the following regions: Svalbard (Norway), the Avannaata Municipality (Greenland), the Beaufort Sea Region (Canada), and the Tiksi/Bykovskiy region (Russia). This pan-Arctic approach allowed us to include the perceptions of risk from diverse geo-political contexts and (Indigenous) populations (Ramage et al. 2022), who are confronted with distinct challenges due to varying physical properties of the prevailing permafrost soils (Irrgang et al. 2022). The qualitative data gathered during that period were firstly pooled through a series of workshops and discussions between the consortium members and local stakeholders. Secondly, we conducted a thematic (network) analysis to classify the data per component of risk, defined as key hazards, physical processes, societal consequences and adaptation practices. This laid the foundation for iteratively ranking the identified

risks by engaging social, engineering, natural and health Nunataryuk scientists to scrutinize the results, derive and verify rankings. The results were then shared with Arctic communities in late 2022 and early 2023 through a series of workshops and interviews, who then further verified and/or modified the outcomes.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The novelty of our research is the comparative approach, spanning different environmental and societal contexts, as well as the multidisciplinary synthesis identifying risks across the case study areas. The primary objective of this study was to conduct an in-depth risk analysis of permafrost thaw, considering both physical processes and societal concerns. Harnessing an inter- and transdisciplinary approach, we drew understandings from diverse disciplines as well as from (Indigenous) land users, rights- and knowledge holders through multidirectional knowledge exchange processes. By synthesizing this information we contribute to a better understanding of the complex and interconnected risks across permafrost landscapes.

DEFINITION OF RISK

We understand risk holistically, as a socio-natural phenomena defined by perceptions of multiple stakeholders (Larsen et al. 2021). Risks arise from the interaction between 1) physical processes, including anthropogenic global warming and pollution; 2) hazards which are set at the intersection of the natural and societal realms; and 3) socio-ecological consequences, corresponding to local perceptions of permafrost thaw impacts. Local perceptions vary significantly depending on socio-economic, political, environmental and other contexts. We define risks as dynamic and rooted in the interconnected relationship between humans and nature, encompassing various perspectives from stakeholders like scientists, regulators, and local landusers and residents (Larsen et al. 2021).

RESULTS: FIVE KEY HAZARDS

Through the comprehensive risk analysis, we identified five key hazards of permafrost thaw, namely:

1) infrastructure failure, 2) disruption of mobility and supply, 3) decreased water quality, 4) challenges for food security, and 5) increased risk of exposure to infectious diseases and contaminants. These key hazards have far-reaching impacts on ecosystems, socio-cultural dynamics, economies, governance and the health and wellbeing of Arctic communities. Their complex interconnectedness is highlighted in a composite overview (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Key Hazards of Permafrost Thaw (adapted from Westerveld et al. 2023)

The risk assessment showed that infrastructure failure and disruption of mobility and supply chains have the largest impacts on costs and economy, and were generally perceived as having the highest societal impacts. Exposure to infectious diseases and contaminants was linked to the highest levels of perceived uncertainty. Challenges for food security, subsistence activities and decrease in water quality were perceived as central in the Beaufort Sea and in the Northeast Siberia regions, but not in Svalbard and Greenland. Hence, depending on factors such as livelihood strategies, socio-cultural and political context, structures of governance, available infrastructure and permafrost conditions, the perception of risks related to permafrost thaw entails significant place- and context-specific complexities, and exhibits substantial variation not only within individuals and communities, but also between regions.

CONCLUSION

The transdisciplinary risk analysis of permafrost thaw along and near Arctic coasts has revealed substantial impacts on the livelihoods of local communities. By synthesizing insights from various disciplines and involving stakeholders in multi-

directional knowledge exchanges, our study enhances the understanding of the intricate factors driving risks in four focal areas. Our research provides pivotal insights into the key risks associated with permafrost thaw in Arctic coastal areas, a framework for future studies in this field, which are necessary to address uncertainties associated with permafrost thaw risks, and underscores the urgent need for proactive adaptive measures.

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